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Research Article

A COMPARATIVE OBSERVATIONAL STUDY SIGNIFYING THE DIVERSITY OF CLINICAL FEATURES IN PATIENTS HAVING TUBERCULOSIS WITH AND WITHOUT RENAL FAILURE

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Abstract:

Objective- Nowadays one of the shocking augmentation renal failure at global level and lots of studies are evident that due to renal failure TB patients suffers most as it not only affect the presentation of TB disease but also its treatment results. The main objective of this study is to examine the clinical features diversity in TB patients who are suffering through renal failure and who are not suffering renal failure.

Material and Methods- The type of this study that was conducted in Holy Family Hospital Rawalpindi was the comparative observational study in which total 107 subjects were selected. All the selected patients were diagnosed of TB disease and these selected patients were divided into two groups on the basis of renal failure. The TB patients who had renal failure were kept in 1st group and those patients who had not renal failure were kept in 2nd group. SPSS ver. 20 was used for statistical analysis. In the form of frequency (%) qualitative data was presented and in form of mean \pm SD quantitative data was presented.

Results- In all the selected patients of both groups 45 (42%) were females and males were 62(58%). In 1st group of TB patients with renal failure the mean age was 64.56 ± 8.77 years and in 2nd group of TB patients without renal failure the mean age was 38.25 ± 12.70 years. The results of both groups were compared thoroughly like clinical features and laboratory values (protein, neutrophils, lymphocytes).

Conclusion- In this study it was concluded that there was a significance difference in clinical feature of TB patients with and without renal failure. The patients of TB with renal failure from group one had diabetes mellitus, pleural effusion, hemoptysis, chest pain, productive cough, and shortness of breath as common features while 2nd group of patients without renal failure had common feature like fatigue, fever, and night sweats.

Keywords: Non-renal failure, renal failure, Pulmonary Tuberculosis

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INTRODUCTION:

Pulmonary tuberculosis or tuberculosis of lungs is that type of infection which is increasing at global level with increasing morbidity or mortality. Although through medicines of anti-TB or other treatments advancement in controlling TB have been achieved but still in many areas or countries TB is spreading at greater level. According to an estimation death due to TB are approximately 1.7 million per annum which means that every minute 3 people are dying due to TB. For the treatment of a TB patients, it is necessary to analyze the intensity or severity of symptoms associated with TB. Its early detection can be very helpful if proper treatment is provided its spread can be control. However, in TB the increasing age of patient can be a reason behind the various morbidities linked with TB and then this can cause even mortality.

The risk of TB is comparatively increased in those patients who have renal failure or chronic kidney disease. In patients of renal failure or chronic kidney disease (CKD) the prime reason of TB infection is diabetes mellitus, HIV infection or cell-mediated impairment immunity. Nowadays one of the shocking augmentation renal failure at global level and lots of studies are evident that due to renal failure TB patients suffers most as it not only affect the presentation of TB disease but also its treatment results. The main objective of this study is to examine the clinical features diversity in TB patients who are suffering through renal failure and who are not suffering renal failure.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The type of this study was the comparative observational study in which total 107 subjects were selected. All the selected patients were diagnosed of TB disease and these selected patients were divided into two groups on the basis of renal failure. The TB patients who had renal failure were kept in 1st group ad those patients who had not renal failure were kept in 2nd group. In this study all those patients were include who had the age between 20 to 70 years included the features of renal failure, respiratory symptoms, pleural effusion, homogenous patch, cavitations, unilateral or bilateral hilar lymphadenopathy, patchy infiltrates, raised ADA

level, no severe co-morbidity, and non-smokers. All those excluded who were smokers, having multiple co-morbidities, pleural fluid findings or no positive sputum. A written consent paper was signed by all the patients after providing them primary counselling about this study. All the patients were investigated through bladder and kidney ureter ultrasound, pleural fluid studies, sputum studies and chest x-ray. On the bases of these investigation anti-TB therapy started on patients. SPSS ver. 20 was used for statistical analysis. In the form of frequency (%) qualitative data was presented and in form of mean \pm SD quantitative data was presented.

RESULTS:

Out of 107 TB patients 66 patients were without renal failure including 28 females and 238 males while 41 patients were with renal failure included 17 females and 24 males. In all the selected patients of both groups 45 (42%) were females and males were 62(58%). In 1st group of TB patients with renal failure the mean age was 64.56 ± 8.77 years and in 2nd group of TB patients without renal failure the mean age was 38.25 ± 12.70 years. The results of both groups were compared thoroughly like clinical features and laboratory values (protein, neutrophils, lymphocytes). The results revealed that there is significant difference in patients of both groups in terms of creatinine level, proteins, low density lipoprotein, neutrophils, lymphocytes, and specific gravity. (Table-1) In 52 patients of non-renal failure night sweats was present while in 3 patients of renal failure it was present. In 60 patients of non-renal failure night fever was present while in 10 patients of renal failure it was present. In 53 patients of non-renal failure fatigue was preset while in 25 patients of renal failure it was present. In 19 patients of non-renal failure shortness of breath was preset while in 19 patients of renal failure it was present. In 28 patients of non-renal failure productive cough was preset while in 40 patients of renal failure it was present. In 18 patients of non-renal failure chest pain was preset while in 37 patients of renal failure it was present. In 20 patients of non-renal failure effusion was preset while in 31 patients of renal failure it was present. In 8 patients of non-renal failure diabetes mellitus was preset while in 32 patients of renal failure it was present. (Table 2)

Table 1. Comparison in TB patients with renal failure and without renal failure

Variables n=107	Renal failure Yes (n=41) Mean \pm SD	Non renal failure (n=66) Mean \pm SD	p- value
Age(years)	64.56 \pm 8.77	38.25 \pm 12.70	<0.001
Urine Specific Gravity	1.03 \pm 0.16	0.46 \pm 0.52	<0.001
Lymphocytes (%)	69.67 \pm 9.22	77.55 \pm 10.65	0.002
Neutrophils (%)	29.22 \pm 11.06	18.86 \pm 10.24	<0.001
Low Density Lipoproteins	874.56 \pm 410.67	328.24 \pm 459.59	<0.001
Proteins	7.13 \pm 0.95	2.77 \pm 3.34	<0.001
Creatinine Clearance	46.63 \pm 7.31	57.86 \pm 7.80	<0.001

Table 1. Association of clinical features with both groups

Variables		Renal failure Yes (n=41) n(%)	Non renal failure(n=66) n(%)	p-value
Gender	Male	24(58.5%)	38(57.6%)	0.922
	Female	17(41.5%)	28(42.4%)	
Night Sweats	Yes	3(7.3%)	52(78.8%)	<0.001
	No	38(92.7%)	14(21.2%)	
Fever	Yes	10(24.4%)	60(90.9%)	<0.001
	No	31(75.6%)	6(9.1%)	
Fatigue	Yes	25(61.0%)	53(80.3%)	0.029
	No	16(39.0%)	13(19.7%)	
Shortness of Breath	Yes	39(95.1%)	19(28.8%)	<0.001
	No	2(4.9%)	47(71.2%)	
Productive Cough	Yes	40(97.6%)	28(42.4%)	<0.001
	No	1(2.4%)	38(57.6%)	
Chest Pain	Yes	37(90.2%)	18(27.3%)	<0.001
	No	4(9.8%)	48(72.7%)	
Hemoptysis	Yes	22(53.7%)	6(9.1%)	<0.001
	No	19(46.3%)	60(90.9%)	
Effusion	Yes	31(75.6%)	20(30.3%)	<0.001
	No	10(24.4%)	46(69.7%)	
History of Diabetes Mellitus	Yes	32(78.0%)	8(12.1%)	<0.001
	No	9(22.0%)	58(87.9%)	

DISCUSSION:

For the treatment of a TB patients, it is necessary to analyze the intensity or severity of symptoms associated with TB. Its early detection can be very helpful if proper treatment is provided its spread can be control. However, in TB the increasing age of patient can be a reason behind the various morbidities linked with TB and then this can cause even mortality. The risk of TB is comparatively increased in those patients who have renal failure or chronic kidney disease. In patients of renal failure or chronic kidney disease (CKD) the prime reason of TB infection is diabetes mellitus, HIV infection or cell-mediated impairment immunity. Nowadays one of the shocking augmentation renal failure at global level and lots of studies are evident that due to renal failure TB patients suffers most as it not only affect the presentation of TB disease but also its treatment results.

Generous contrasts were seen in our examination in pneumonic tuberculosis patients with or without renal disappointment with respect to TB explicit just as vague indications. Indications, for example, fever, weariness, night sweats, windedness, profitable hack, chest torment, hemoptysis, pleural emission all were answered to have critical contrasts.

In another examination revealed that about 68.7% of patients with TB in their examination had constant kidney sickness. 20 % of patients among them were on hemodialysis. 75 % of the patients had extra-asperatory TB. Pleuro-pneumonic (41.8%), kidney and urinary lot (20%), stomach and lymph hub (13% each) were most generally noted site of TB. Our investigation just included asperatory tuberculosis patients with or without renal disappointment. Despite the fact that fever was available in a comparable recurrence in patients, i.e., 24.4% of TB patients having renal disappointment However a higher rate of pleural emission was seen in our investigation, for example in 75.6% of patients having attending renal disappointment potentially because of the way that solitary pneumonic tuberculosis patients were chosen in our examination.

CONCLUSION:

In this study it was concluded that there was a significance difference in clinical feature of TB patients with and without renal failure. The patients of TB with renal failure from group one had diabetes mellitus, pleural effusion, hemoptysis, chest pain, productive cough, and shortness of breath as common features while 2nd group of patients without renal failure had common feature like fatigue, fever, and night sweats.

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